

UNIVERSITY OF DELAWARE
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Additive Preform Molding of 3D High-Performance Continuous Carbon Fiber Thermoset Composites

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Energy Efficiency &
Renewable Energy

Composite Manufacturing Challenges

Molding

Open Mold Process

Types:

- Hand Lay Up
- Spray Up
- Filament winding

Closed Mold Process

Types:

- Compression molding
- Vacuum bagging
- Resin Film Infusion

Challenges:

- Labor Intensive
- Difficulty in producing complex shapes
- Difficult to maintain uniform thickness

Additive Manufacturing

Types:

- Fused Deposition Modeling
- Direct Ink Writing
- Automated Fiber Placement

Niendorf K. and Rayemaekers, *Adv. Eng. Mat.*, 2021

Challenges:

- Anisotropic behavior
- Weak interlaminar bonding
- Cannot fabricate complex shapes

Research Objectives

Continuous fiber-reinforced **3D part fabrication**

- Load based **optimal fiber alignment** for out of plane orientation
- **Complete part reinforcement** with continuous Fibers
- Allows for precise **3D composite fabrication**

Optimize **fiber orientation**

Proposed Solution

— Carbon Fiber ■ Dual cure resin ■ Epoxy resin ■ Base ■ Mold

Preform Printing

- Dual-cured resin (UV + thermal) coating
- Uncured epoxy matrix

Preform Reconfiguring

- Transformation from 2D to 3D
- In-plane to through plane reinforcement

Molding

- Ensures geometry formation of the part
- Enhanced continuous fiber alignment

Additive Preform Molding (APM)

- **Dual-cure resin shell:** bonds the interlayers and forms the preform structure.
- **Epoxy core (uncured):** provides flexibility for bending during forming process.
- **Mold:** ensures geometry of the preform composite is maintained during heating.

Preform Properties, Reconfiguring and Molding

Semi-cured preform towpreg

- ✓ Can retain its structure
- ✓ Reconfigurable
- ✓ Near net shape fabrication
- ✓ Alignment controlled

Pristine Preform

Reconfiguring

Bending

Twisting

Composite Bracket Fabrication via APM Process

2D Preform

No need for reconfiguration for planar 2D bracket

Preform Reconfiguration

Overmolding

3D Reconfigured Bracket

Samples

Enhancement of Interlayer Bonding (IPN Formation)

- **Formation Method:**

Sequential polymerization of the two polymer networks

- **DMA Evidence:**

Broad $\tan(\delta)$ transitions in epoxy/UV blends

→ Indicate overlapping relaxations from two polymer networks

→ Support full IPN formation due to the interpenetration of distinct polymer networks

Short Fiber Reinforcement and Overmolding

Short fiber reinforcement:

- 0.5 wt% short fibers (1~5 mm) in epoxy

Effect of Short Fiber Reinforcement on Flexural Properties

Overmolding:

- 120 °C under a pressure of 1 MPa for 4 hours

Effect of Overmolding on ILSS

Microstructural Analysis 3D Reconfigured Bracket

Microstructural analysis of the joint region:

Highlights the distribution of:
fibers, matrix, and pores

- Fibers conform to the geometric change
- Effective fiber alignment

Joint region (raw CT)

Cropped image 12.4 x 10.2 mm

CF Matrix

Mechanical Characterization of APM Composites

- APM (★) shows tensile strength >1000 MPa, with modulus > 100 GPa at coupon level.
- Outperforms most AM thermoset & thermoplastic composites (especially continuous fiber based).

Conclusions

- **Additive Preform Molding (APM)** is developed for near-net-shaped 3D continuous carbon fiber composites.
- Reconfigurable preforms achieved via dual-cure resin and fiber alignment control.
- Overmolding leads to 35.7% increase in interlaminar shear strength (ILSS).
- Achieved >1000 MPa tensile strength and >100 GPa modulus at coupon level.
- APM outperforms most continuous carbon fiber composites from AM.

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